

Extended data – Investigating the cortical mechanisms of conspecific voice perception in anesthetized marmosets using 3T fMRI: Individual activations

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Figure 1 **Results of monkey M1 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast.** (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.

Figure 2 Results of monkey M3 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast. (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.

M4 - Sound vs. silence

M4 - Marmoset voc. vs. scrambled

Figure 3 **Results of monkey M4 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast.** (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.

Figure 4 **Results of monkey M5 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast.** (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.

Figure 5 Results of monkey M8 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast. (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.

Figure 6 Results of monkey M9 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast. (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.

M10 - Sound vs. silence

M10 - Marmoset voc. vs. scrambled

Figure 7 Results of monkey M10 for sound > silence contrast and for marmoset vocalization > scrambled contrast. (A) and (C) Brain activation t-maps displayed on both the left and right fiducial brain surface template (Liu et al., 2021), with the lateral view presented at the top and the medial view at the bottom. The delineation of regions based on an atlas (Paxinos et al., 2012) is depicted by white lines. (B) and (D) Volumetric activations are superimposed onto coronal slices of subject anatomical brain images.